

A. Classifier Performance Analysis

Table 1

This Table presents the average classification results obtained by fine-tuning XLNet for sentiment analysis 10 times on varying data.

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Negative	0.815	0.833	0.823	3016.3
Positive	0.827	0.808	0.818	2983.7
Accuracy			0.821	6000
Macro Average	0.821	0.821	0.820	6000
Weighted Average	0.821	0.821	0.821	6000

Table 2

This Table presents the average classification results obtained by fine-tuning XLNet for hate speech detection 10 times using 5-fold cross-validation.

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
No Hate	0.949	0.962	0.955	3594.1
Hate	0.923	0.916	0.920	2405.9
Accuracy			0.944	6000
Macro Average	0.936	0.939	0.937	6000
Weighted Average	0.939	0.944	0.941	6000

A.1. XLNet_Hate performance analysis

Since the performance of XLNet_Hate is unusually high the trained model was used to classify 20K posts from the HateXplain dataset by (Mathew et al., 2021). The classification results were then compared to the manually annotated labels. The confusion matrix of the classification results on HateXplain can be found in Figure 1a.

Figure 1: This figure shows the confusion matrix of labels predicted by XLNet_Hate and manually annotated labels with different thresholds.

The confusion matrix shows a large portion of false positives. This is an indicator of the threshold of when a post is classified as hate (for XLNet_hate set at 0.5) being too low. The classification was repeated with higher thresholds of 0.85 and 0.99. Higher thresholds do minimize the false positive classifications. They however equally increase false negatives. So that the overall F1-score only varies marginally when the threshold is changed. A higher

threshold would lead to a decreased share of hate classifications in the BAT dataset. With a threshold of 0.99 the share of classified hate drops for BAT to 5.9%. We base our choice of threshold on existing work in the domain, but also compare distributions of labels for various thresholds, to evaluate the tradeoff between false positives and false negatives. To assure reliability of our labels, we inspect the quality of classifications manually, as described in section 4.2.2. As we mention in the introduction, we publish all data, models, and thresholds anonymously at https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/10VAKG0io7NlSPzL0uuraKA0oQ_K8J9-8?usp=sharing to ensure that future improvements on the classifications can be made, and to enhance transparency of our research.